

CHALLENGES CONFRONTING MUSLIM SINGLE MOTHERS DURING THE WAITING PERIOD: AN EXPLORATION OF EMOTIONAL, FINANCIAL, AND SOCIAL ASPECTS.

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ABSTRACT

The waiting period is bound to be observed by the divorcees, widows and left behind women among Muslim community. It is called as Iddah and the time duration is fixed to three months for divorcees, four months and ten days for widows, and up to a maximum 7 years for left behind women. The Iddah is deeply rooted in Islamic jurisprudence, refers to the waiting period that Muslim women are obligated to observe following the dissolution of a marriage through divorce or the death of a spouse. This prescribed waiting period serves several significant purposes within the Islamic legal framework. First and foremost, Iddah allows for the verification of any potential pregnancy resulting from the dissolved union, ensuring clarity in matters of lineage and inheritance. Beyond its legal and practical implications, Iddah carries a profound symbolic significance, providing a designated time for emotional healing, reflection, and spiritual renewal. This study delves into the multifaceted challenges encountered by Muslim single mother during the Iddah period, a distinctive phase following divorce or the death of a spouse. It is also mandatory for left behind single mothers whose husband is disappear due to natural calamities and accidents. Through an examination of emotional, financial, and social aspects, the research sheds light on the nuanced experiences of single mothers. Emotional distress, financial strain, and social stigma emerge as prominent themes, each influenced by cultural, societal, and individual factors through literature reviews. The study underscores the need for a comprehensive understanding of the complexities during the Iddah period, aiming to contribute to discussions on support systems, societal perceptions, and potential interventions to alleviate the difficulties faced by Muslim single women during this transitional phase.

KEY WORDS: Iddah, Waiting Period, widows, divorcees and Left behind single mothers.

INTRODUCTION

Islam is a religion with universal characteristics, a worldview of equality, justice, takaful, freedom, and dignity, and a humanistic concept of theocentric (Setiyawan, A. 2012). Islam is a total way of life, a complete system governing all aspects of man's existence, both individual and collective (Zaman, H. 1997). It has unique beliefs and ritual practices to be followed during the special occasions like birth, death and divorce, and the festivals. A ritual comprises a sequence of actions carried out by humans within the realm of the sacred (Durkheim, E. 1912). The study focuses on the ritual practice performed by the divorcees, widows and left behind women to untie the marriage bond with the husband. The time duration is fixed to three months for divorcees, four months and ten days for widows, and up to a maximum 7 years for left behind women (Meryaniwal, F. & Talwasa, S. 2021). Iddah is observed in a closed room at her husband's home where she lived. This prescribed waiting period serves several significant purposes within the Islamic legal framework. First and foremost, Iddah allows for the verification of any potential pregnancy resulting from the dissolved union, ensuring clarity in matters of lineage and inheritance. Beyond its legal and practical implications, Iddah carries a profound symbolic significance, providing a designated time for emotional healing, reflection, and spiritual renewal (Rahayu Mulia Romadoni 2019). This study delves into the multifaceted challenges encountered by Muslim single mother during the iddah period, a distinctive phase following divorce or the death of a spouse. It is also mandatory for left behind single mothers whose husband is disappear due to natural calamities and accidents.

What does the Quran say about iddah?

The Quran, Sunnah and Hadith are the foundations of Islam. It is believed by the Muslims that Quran is the words of god; the Sunnah encompasses the firmly established guidance found in the overall conduct of the Prophet Mohamed, including his path, methodology, and way. The hadith refers to any incident attributed to the Prophet, regardless of whether it occurred only once in his life or was narrated by just one person. The iddah ritual practice is mentioned in the Quran, Sunnah and Hadith. Since Quran is the most authentic and followed by its maximum followers the verses mentioned in the Quran is given below:-

- And those of you who die and leave wives behind them, they (the wives) shall wait (as regards their marriage) for four months and ten days. [al-Baqarah 2:234]
- And divorced women shall wait (as regards their marriage) for three menstrual periods. [al-Baqarah 2:228]
- And for those who are pregnant (whether they are divorced or their husbands are dead), their Iddah (prescribed period) is until they lay down their burden. [al-Talaq 4:65]

Verification of Pregnancy:

One of the primary purposes of Iddah is to ascertain whether the woman is pregnant as a result of the dissolved marriage or the death of her spouse. This verification is essential for determining issues related to lineage and inheritance, ensuring clarity in matters of family and legal rights. Iddah, a waiting period after divorce or death of a husband, has medical advantages for women with menopause, amenorrhea, and pregnancy, as explained by Quranic interpretation and medical knowledge (Musyafaah, N. 2018).

- *Legal and Lineage Clarification:* Iddah serves as a legal requirement to verify whether the woman is pregnant from the dissolved marriage. This verification is crucial for matters of lineage and inheritance, ensuring that there is clarity about the child's parentage and rights to inheritance.
- *Spiritual and Emotional Healing:* Beyond its legal implications, Iddah provides a designated time for emotional healing, reflection, and spiritual renewal. This waiting period is seen as a time for self-discovery and personal growth, allowing individuals to come to terms with the changes in their lives.
- *Symbolic and Moral Significance:* The waiting period also holds symbolic significance in Islam, emphasizing the sanctity of the marital relationship and the need for a thoughtful and considered approach to divorce. It underscores the seriousness of the decision and provides an opportunity for reconciliation if possible.
- *Community and Social Order:* Iddah helps maintain social order by preventing hasty remarriages and potential complications arising from uncertain paternity. It reinforces the importance of respecting the sanctity of the marital bond and promotes a sense of responsibility among the community.

In the lens of Islam, the Iddah plays a vital role in reshaping the women's mental health towards the positive. Furthermore, this study delves into the multifaceted challenges faced by Muslim single mothers during the Iddah period, a distinctive phase following divorce or the death of a spouse. Additionally, it explores the mandatory Iddah period for single mothers left behind due to husbands disappearing amid natural calamities or accidents. Through a comprehensive examination of emotional, financial, and social dimensions, the research sheds light on the nuanced experiences of single mothers navigating this transitional phase. Prominent themes, such as emotional distress, financial strain, and social stigma, are explored within the context of cultural, societal, and individual factors through an extensive review of relevant literature. As the study unfolds, it underscores the imperative of cultivating a comprehensive understanding of the complexities surrounding the Iddah period. By doing so, the research aims to contribute valuable insights to discussions on support systems, societal perceptions, and potential interventions geared towards alleviating the myriad difficulties faced by Muslim single women during this challenging and transformative phase of their lives. Single mothers during the Iddah period face a range of challenges.

OBJECTIVES

The present study designed to address the social Stigma experienced by the widowed, divorced and left behind single mothers. It is abstracted to examine the cultural expectations of the Muslim community over iddah observed single mothers and to analyse the issues in Interacting with iddah observed single mothers and how are they excluded from the normalcy. It is to understand the financial strain and emotional distress of the divorced, widowed and left behind single mothers. The study is intended to interrogate the parental challenges and responsibilities during iddah and the post-iddah period. And it is aimed to navigate the potential reconciliation of single mothers and community support throughout the waiting period. Also the study concentrates on the legal, inheritance issues and hindrance over personal growth and identity of the widowed, divorced and left behind single mothers.

METHODOLOGY

The study employed Qualitative meta-analysis research design to address the issues and challenges faced by the widowed, divorced and left behind single mothers among Muslim community. This design concentrates on extracting in-depth and detailed information from a limited set of relevant studies. The study aimed to systematically assess the primary qualitative research findings of the previous studies with accuracy (Ahn, E., & Kang, H. 2018). The scope of using this design is to provide a comprehensive understanding of the lived experiences of the respondents. The principles of data saturation, research objectives and availability of the study limited the number of reviewing articles to 42. Until the new theme and information stop arising, the researcher continued analysing the various studies on iddah, divorced, widowed and left behind single mothers among Muslim community.

Qualitative Meta- analysis

Qualitative meta-analysis is designed to amalgamate qualitative findings derived from case studies (Hoon 2013). Qualitative case studies stand out for their ability to offer in-depth insights into specific contextual factors or to illuminate the reasons behind certain phenomena that are typically beyond the scope of quantitative investigations (Rauch 2020; Rauch et al. 2014). In a qualitative meta-analysis, the identified case studies undergo systematic coding within a meta-synthesis protocol. It involves the organized coding and synthesis of identified case studies. The protocol outlines the methodological steps and guidelines for systematically analyzing and extracting key information from individual case studies. This process is crucial for identifying influential variables, recognizing patterns, and ultimately constructing a comprehensive meta-causal network that synthesizes the qualitative findings across multiple studies. The meta-synthesis protocol serves as a methodological roadmap to ensure consistency, rigor, and transparency in the qualitative synthesis of information from diverse sources.

A LOOK THROUGH SOCIOLOGICAL LENSES

Theoretical understanding always guides the researcher to have a clear view over the practical issues. Structural-Functionalism, Conflict Theory, Symbolic Interactionism and Feminism perspectives were used to explain the underlying influences of single motherhood. And it is used to study the emotional, financial, and social aspects of single mothers who experienced iddah. Also it helps to analyse how ritual practice influences the experiences of widowed, divorced and left behind single mothers. Through the structural-functionalist perspective, the researcher understood the causes of single motherhood and its impact on the stability and functioning of the family as a social unit. It helped to explore how single mothers navigate traditional family roles and how their absence of a male partner influences family dynamics. Conflict theory helped the researcher on power imbalances and social inequalities. In the context of single motherhood, the researcher examined how economic disparities, gender roles, and systemic inequalities contribute to the challenges that are faced by widowed, divorced and left behind single mothers among Muslim community. The study also explored the issues related to child support, employment opportunities, and access to resources.

Symbolic interactionist's views are interested in how individuals construct meaning and interpret symbols within social interactions. The researcher used this perspective to study how single mothers perceive themselves and are perceived by society. They explored the labels, stereotypes, and social expectations associated with single motherhood. Feminism perspective helped the investigator to examine the confrontations of single motherhood within the broader context of gender roles and patriarchal structures. The researcher analyzed how societal expectations around motherhood and family contribute to the challenges faced by single mothers and advocate for gender equality in family spheres among Muslim community.

DATA SYNTHESIS

The researcher identified the following themes as an outcome of qualitative meta-analysis namely Social Stigma and Judgment, Cultural Expectations, Limited Social Interactions, Financial Strain, Emotional Distress, Parental Responsibilities, Navigating Potential Reconciliation and Community Support, Legal and Inheritance Issues, Personal Growth and Identity. It is found that the issues and challenges of the respondents varied from one geographical area to another. The objectives of the study limited the boundary and helped in what to exclude and include.

Social Stigma and Judgment

Stigma can be described as the condition in which an individual is excluded from complete social acceptance (Goffman, 1963, p. 9). Muslim single mothers are manifesting social stigma even after observing iddah. The widowed, divorced and left behind single mothers are considered as bad luck if they meet people in the ceremonies and festivals. Jones and colleagues (1984) suggest that stigma undergoes moderation through six factors: concealability, course, disruptiveness, aesthetic qualities, origin, and peril. Concealability pertains to how noticeable a stigmatizing attribute is; for instance, skin colour is often visible, while mental illness can be concealed. While readily visible stigmas result in immediate discrimination, concealable stigmas carry other adverse consequences. Even though a stigma like mental illness can be concealed in certain situations, managing information about it—deciding whom to disclose it to, who not to, how to keep records hidden—can lead to heightened levels of social stress and strained social interactions (Beatty & Kirby, 2004; Clair, Beatty, & MacLean, 2005; Joachim & Acorn, 2000). Discrimination arising from visible stigmas might be easier to detect and legally address than discrimination based on invisible attributes (Stefan, 2000). Among the other dimensions outlined by Jones and colleagues, course and peril have emerged as significant influences on the extent of stigma and its negative behavioural consequences (Jorm & Griffiths, 2008; Keller, 2005; Link et al., 1999). In recent years, several researchers have also started to investigate the impact of various explanatory models or causal beliefs concerning the origins and nature of mental illness (Phelan, 2005; Rusch et al., 2010; Schomerus et al., 2012; Schomerus, Matschinger, & Angermeyer, 2013). Social stigma for Muslim single mothers manifest as societal disapproval or negative attitudes directed towards these women due to their hidden attributes or social status as unmarried mothers within the Muslim community. This stigma arises from cultural or religious norms that emphasize traditional family structures. Muslim single mothers face judgment, stereotyping, or isolation, leading to challenges in social acceptance and support. It's essential to recognize and address such stigma to foster inclusivity and understanding within diverse communities. Single Muslim women are facing societal judgment or stigma, especially in communities where divorce or widowhood is stigmatized. This can lead to feelings of isolation and a sense of being scrutinized.

Cultural Expectations

Cultural norms and expectations surrounding the Iddah period is varying widely, adding an additional layer of complexity. Balancing religious requirements with cultural practices pose challenges for some women. During Iddah, women are often expected to observe a degree of social seclusion. This means limiting social interactions, refraining from adornment, and avoiding situations that could lead to a potential new marriage proposal (Romadoni, R. 2019). Women in Iddah adopt more modest clothing and avoid using cosmetics or adornments as a sign of mourning

and withdrawal from regular social activities. Cultural norms may dictate that a woman in Iddah stays in her marital home, especially if she is mourning the death of her husband. In the case of divorce, she continues to reside in the same home during the waiting period (Jonker, G. 1997).. A woman is not allowed to marry or engage in any marriage negotiations. This period serves as a time of reflection and adjustment before considering a new marital commitment. Cultural expectations often include providing emotional support and sympathy to a woman in Iddah, especially if she has lost her spouse. Friends and family may offer assistance and companionship during this challenging time. Iddah is not only a cultural practice but also has religious significance in Islam. Women engage in increased religious observances, including prayer, recitation of the Quran, and seeking spiritual solace (Nurohim, M., Pasaribu, Y. H., & Asmaiyani, A. 2021).

Limited Social Interactions

Meaningful social interaction play a crucial role in maintaining both our physical and mental health (Sun, Harris, & Vazrie, 2020), especially in periods marked by stress (Lippold et al., 2016; Sachser et al., 1998). From the moment of birth, individuals are inherently social beings, seeking connection, understanding, and support from others. Meaningful social interactions have been linked to stress reduction. Engaging in positive and supportive conversations with others helps alleviate stress, which is a common precursor to various physical health issues. Scientific studies have shown that regular social interactions contribute to the enhancement of the immune system. The emotional support and companionship derived from social connections positively impact the body's ability to combat illnesses and diseases.

Numerous studies suggest a correlation between strong social ties and increased life expectancy. Meaningful social interaction fosters a sense of belonging, purpose, and security, contributing to a longer and healthier life. Sharing thoughts, concerns, and joys with others creates a support system that acts as a buffer against mental health challenges. Individuals with robust social connections are less susceptible to depression and anxiety. The emotional bonds formed through meaningful interactions contribute to a sense of stability and resilience in the face of life's challenges. Social engagement has been linked to better cognitive function and a reduced risk of cognitive decline in later years. Conversations, discussions, and shared activities stimulate the brain, promoting mental acuity. Conversely, social isolation and loneliness can lead to adverse health effects, both physically and mentally. The lack of meaningful connections may contribute to a higher risk of chronic diseases and mental health disorders. Iddah involves a period of restricted social interactions, which contributes to feelings of loneliness and isolation, particularly for those who were part of a married couple (Jonker, G. 1997).

Financial Strain

Economic challenges may arise, especially if the woman was financially dependent on her spouse. Navigating financial independence during Iddah is a significant concern. Iddah in Indonesia does not provide an opportunity for the wife to earn a living, which is not in line with gender justice and equality of men and women (Maulida, F., & Busyro, B. 2018). The financial strain experienced by Muslim widows and divorcees is challenging aspect of their post-marital life. Several factors contribute to the economic difficulties faced by these women, and it's crucial to understand and address these issues. Most Muslim women often rely on their husbands for financial support. The death of a spouse or divorce may result in an abrupt loss of this support, leaving the widow or divorcee without a primary source of income. Widows and divorcees, especially those who have been out of the workforce for an extended period, may face challenges in finding suitable employment. Limited job opportunities can exacerbate financial strain. Cultural norms and social stigma in certain communities impact the ability of widows and divorcees to access financial resources or support. Discrimination hinders their participation in economic activities and limits their financial independence.

Muslim widows and divorcees still bear financial responsibilities, such as caring for children or meeting other family needs. Balancing these responsibilities with limited financial resources is overwhelming. In some cases, widows face challenges in asserting their rights to property or

inheritance. Legal and cultural factors affect their ability to secure financial assets that rightfully belong to them. A lack of financial literacy and awareness contribute to the financial strain experienced by widows and divorcees. Understanding financial management, investments, and available support systems is essential for navigating economic challenges.

Emotional Distress

The emotional aftermath of a divorce or the death of a spouse is particularly challenging. Iddah requires women to confront and navigate these emotions during a specified waiting period (Aditya.B.A.P.2020).. The emotional distress experienced by Muslim widows, single mothers, and left-behind women is a poignant aspect of their lives, reflecting the challenges associated with loss, societal expectations, and the complexities of their roles. The death of a spouse brings profound grief, leaving Muslim widows grappling with the emotional void created by the loss of a life partner. Coping with the absence of companionship and the transition to singlehood contributes to emotional distress. Separation or divorce often places single mothers in emotionally challenging circumstances. The dissolution of a marriage leads to feelings of failure, rejection, and the burden of sole responsibility for children. Women left behind among Muslim community due to migration or other factors may experience emotional distress associated with the absence of their spouses. Longing, uncertainty, and the challenges of maintaining familial bonds across distances contribute to their emotional struggles.

Parental Responsibilities

If there are children from the marriage, single Muslim women experience challenges in managing the emotional and practical aspects of co-parenting or single parenting during Iddah. Single mothers within the Muslim community shoulder unique parental responsibilities, navigating the challenges of raising children on their own while upholding cultural and religious values. Single mothers play a crucial role in providing emotional support to their children, offering a nurturing environment that fosters a sense of security and belonging. This involves open communication, active listening, and addressing the emotional needs of their children. Single mothers often take on the responsibility of instilling Islamic values and teachings in their children (Duval, E. and Miller, C. M. 1985). This includes imparting religious education, teaching moral principles, and fostering a strong connection to their faith. Preserving cultural identity is important for many Muslim families. Single mothers strive to pass on cultural traditions, practices, and languages to ensure that their children maintain a connection to their heritage.

Single mothers actively engage in their children's education, monitoring academic progress, attending parent-teacher meetings, and encouraging a positive attitude towards learning. Single mothers are tasked with the day-to-day management of household affairs. This includes organizing routines, ensuring a healthy living environment, and addressing logistical challenges without the presence of a co-parent. Single mothers encourage self-reliance, problem-solving skills, and a strong work ethic, preparing their children for the challenges of adulthood. Recognizing the importance of a support system, single mothers often build networks within the community, seeking assistance from family, friends, and local resources (Devito, J. A. (1997)). This support network plays a vital role in overcoming the challenges of single parenthood. Single mothers guide their children in spiritual growth, encouraging them to develop a personal relationship with god, participate in religious activities, and integrate Islamic principles into their daily lives.

Navigating Potential Reconciliation and Community Support

For women going through divorce, the Iddah period is a time during which reconciliation is possible. Navigating the complexities of deciding whether to reconcile or proceed with the divorce can be emotionally taxing. The level of support from the community and family members can vary. Some women may find a robust support system, while others may struggle with a lack of understanding or empathy (Klass, D., & Goss, R. (2002)).

Legal and Inheritance Issues

Addressing legal complexities, such as matters related to custody, inheritance, or property rights are the challenges faced by single Muslim women during Iddah. The application of Islamic law (Sharia)

varies across different jurisdictions and cultural contexts, leading to diverse challenges. In some traditional interpretations of Islamic law, inheritance is typically distributed among male family members, such as sons, fathers, and brothers, with specific shares allocated based on relationships. Single mothers find themselves navigating these traditional inheritance norms, potentially facing limitations on their entitlement. Custody and guardianship of children are critical legal issues for Muslim single mothers (Kristiansen, M., & Sheikh, A. 2012).

Sharia provides guidelines for custody arrangements, generally favouring the mother for younger children. Single mothers encounter challenges in securing financial support from the father of their children. Sharia emphasizes the father's responsibility for providing financial support to his children, but the legal enforcement and implementation of these obligations varies. Muslim-majority countries and communities have specific requirements for the recognition of marriages and divorces. Single mothers face hurdles if their marital status or divorce is not officially recognized, impacting their legal rights and entitlements. Sharia outlines specific rules regarding property distribution, and single mothers may find themselves navigating these rules when it comes to properties acquired during marriage or inherited assets. Legal systems influence the extent to which these rules are applied.

Personal Growth and Identity

Societal and cultural norms play an important role in shaping the identity of the single mothers. Cultural expectations regarding family structures, gender roles, and the stigma associated with divorce or widowhood that also influence their self-perception. Regardless of the circumstances, all of them share the common identity of being single mothers. This involves assuming the responsibilities of sole parenting, making decisions for the family, providing emotional and financial support (Kristiansen, M., & Sheikh, A. 2012). The identity of widowed, divorced, and left-behind single mothers often includes a process of rebuilding and personal growth like education, career goals, or engaging in personal development activities. The identity of widowed single mothers involves preserving and honouring the memory of their late spouse. Balancing this with the need to move forward and build a new life is a complex aspect of their identity. Also the previous studies confirmed that the waiting period is an opportunity for personal growth and self-discovery.

CONCLUSION

The transition from focusing solely on sex to embracing the concept of gender and the shift from women's studies to gender studies substantial progress has occurred during 1960s and early 1970s. It marked a vital moment among the developing countries. Before witnessing a significant transformation in both academic and activist realms of women's studies the present study is primarily centered on women, relegating men to the margins. Globally, Muslim women express widespread concern about achieving gender equality through women's empowerment. The status of women among Muslim community reflects unequal dynamics perpetuated by patriarchal structures rooted in male superiority, female inferiority, stereotyped gender roles, and the economic, social, and political dominance of men with women in a position of dependency. Over the past few decades, there has been extensive discourse on women's issues and concerns, with equality standing out as a major focal point among Muslim community. Despite recognizing women's significant contributions to various economic, social, and political activities, achieving true equality remains an elusive goal. Women's movements deserve credit for highlighting the challenges faced by women and facilitating their participation in diverse spheres of life. The journey of Muslim women from mere survival to gaining dignity and empowerment has been arduous. While considerable progress has been made, there is still much ground to cover. Muslim women encounter significant disadvantages, evident in discriminatory practices throughout their life cycle. Early marriages, multiple pregnancies, the birth of underweight babies, and susceptibility to various diseases, lack of mental health and financial literacy underscore the challenges that women among Muslim community continue to face. The emotional distress experienced by Muslim widows, single mothers, and left-behind women is a complex interplay of grief, societal expectations and financial challenges. Recognizing and addressing these emotional struggles requires a holistic approach that encompasses community

support, mental health awareness and initiatives aimed at empowering these women. By fostering understanding and empathy, societies contribute to creating environments that promote healing, resilience, and the overall well-being of these resilient individuals.

Community support and assistance programs play a crucial role in alleviating financial strain. Establishing networks that provide financial guidance, vocational training, or job placement services can empower these women to improve their economic situation. Ensuring that legal frameworks protect the financial rights of Muslim widows and divorcees is vital. Legal reforms that promote gender equality in matters of inheritance and financial entitlements contribute to their economic well-being. Single mothers within the Muslim community undertake multifaceted parental responsibilities, navigating the complexities of raising children while upholding Islamic values and cultural identity. Their resilience, dedication, and commitment contribute significantly to the well-being and development of their families within the context of the Muslim community. Single mothers must enforce rules and expectations while providing guidance and support, recognizing the importance of love and discipline in child rearing. Navigating these legal and inheritance issues requires an understanding of both Islamic principles and local legal contexts. In some instances, legal reforms and community advocacy efforts aim to address these challenges and provide greater support for Muslim single mothers within the framework of Islamic law. Single mothers face challenges related to their legal status and documentation, especially if they were married in a manner not recognized by the local legal system. This affects their ability to access certain rights and benefits. Inheritance distribution becomes a source of dispute within families. Muslim Single mothers need to navigate potential conflicts with other heirs, and the resolution of these disputes influenced by local legal practices and cultural norms. Single mothers encounter difficulties accessing legal resources, especially if they lack financial means. In some cases, legal aid services or community organizations assist in providing support and guidance. Legal and inheritance issues for Muslim single mothers vary widely based on cultural norms, regional interpretations of Islamic law, and the legal frameworks of the country they reside in. It's essential to consider these variations when addressing specific legal challenges. Muslim-majority countries and communities are working towards legal reforms to address issues faced by single mothers, advocating for changes in inheritance laws, custody rights, and other legal aspects that impact their well-being. The life course perspective and intersectionality perspectives also can be used to understand the emotional, financial and social issues of the single mothers focuses on the various transitions and stages individuals go through over their lifetimes. Sociologists studying single motherhood from this perspective might investigate how becoming a single mother impacts a woman's life trajectory, including education, career, and relationships. Intersectionality considers how various social categories, such as race, class, and gender, intersect to shape individuals' experiences. Sociologists examining single motherhood through an intersectional lens would explore how factors like race and socioeconomic status compound the challenges faced by single mothers. Beyond its legal and practical implications, Iddah carries a profound symbolic significance, providing a designated time for emotional healing, reflection, and spiritual renewal.

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